

INFLUENCE OF INTERFACIAL CHARACTERISTICS ON THE NONLINEAR DEFORMATIONS OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The nonlinear stress-strain behavior and ultimate failure of microcomposites were predicted as a function of important interfacial parameters. The microcomposite is the unit cell of Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs). It consists of a single fiber coated with concentric layers of interfacial material and matrix. Important trends in the influence of interfaces upon the stress-strain behaviour were found in agreement with available experimental data for CMCs.

1- INTRODUCTION

The effect of interphase properties and interfacial damage on stress-strain response of CMCs has been evidenced by several experimental studies on 1D [1] and 2D [2, 3] composites and on microcomposites [4].

Fiber/matrix interphases favor crack deflection, eventual further matrix cracking and fiber pull-out. A dense network of matrix cracks is created in the presence of rather strong fiber/matrix interactions and short interfacial cracks [3, 5] whereas fiber pull-out requires rather weak fiber/matrix interactions. The former effect is preferred in 2D CVI composites whereas the latter one is recommended for a variety of 1D composites. The related stress-strain curves exhibit typical features. In the presence of weak fiber/matrix interfacial regions, a plateau-like stress-strain curve is obtained (figure 1) : the nonlinear domain attributed to matrix cracking occurs over a narrow range of stresses and strains and the stress at matrix cracking saturation is much lower than ultimate strength. On the contrast, in the presence of rather strong interfaces, the stresses are higher, the nonlinear domain is wider and the stress at saturation is now close to or coincides with ultimate strength. The deformation behaviors for a range of interphase properties are summarized on figure 1.

There have been several attempts in the literature directed at predicting basic features of the stress-strain response of CMC including the onset of matrix cracking [5-8] and ultimate strength for unidirectional ceramic matrix composites [9-12]. Relatively little effort has been devoted to subsequent accumulation of matrix cracks and the associated nonlinear stress-strain response prior to failure [13, 14].

The primary intent of the present paper is therefore to establish the constitutive equations which describe the influence of interfacial characteristics upon the stress-strain response of microcomposites. A microcomposite consists of a concentric cylinder element containing a single

fiber, with a coating plus a matrix annulus. It is representative of constituents in the actual composite. The microcomposite configuration is thus appropriate for designing interphases, and for investigating fiber/matrix interactions [4] and their influence upon matrix cracking, fiber fracture and the associated stress-strain relations. The load displacement curves measured under tension exhibit the typical features previously discussed with practical CMCs. The load-displacement curves obtained for various microcomposites are summarized on figure 2.

2- ANALYTICAL RELATIONSHIPS

Matrix cracks form sequentially at increasing applied stresses, as reflected by the load displacement curves (figure 2) and acoustic emission recorded on microcomposites under tensile loading [4, 15]. Damage and ultimate failure of CMCs are governed by brittle fracture of the constituents.

Debonding induced by the matrix cracks affects locally the applied stress-field creating stress gradients in the fiber and in the matrix over the region delineated by debonding, as exemplified by figure 3. Stress gradients are linear when a constant interfacial shear stress is assumed. Stresses in the fiber are maximum in the portion where deformations are not prevented by interactions with the matrix, over the distance $u + l_0$, ($2u$ is the crack opening displacement and l_0 is the distance along which Poisson's effect is dominant).

The following equation was used to describe the shear stress τ along the interface as a function of applied stress σ :

$$\tau(x) = (\tau_0 + k\sigma) \alpha(x) \tag{1}$$

where τ_0 is the interfacial shear resistance, k is a coefficient accounting for subsequent fiber/matrix interactions as a function of σ in the debond portion of the microcomposite, involving friction, residual stresses and Poisson's effect. When compression of the interface is dominant, $k > 0$. When the interface is in residual tension, $k < 0$. The function $\alpha(x)$ describes τ variations along the interface. In the present paper, a step function ⁽¹⁾ was selected for $\alpha(x)$ (figure 3), thus subdividing the microcomposite into three different regions, in the vicinity of a matrix crack :

- (i) region 1 : $\alpha(x) = 0$ and $\tau(x) = 0$ for $0 < x < u+l_0$
- (ii) region 2 : $\alpha(x) = 1$ along the debond ($u+l_0 < x < u+l_d$)
- (iii) region 3 : the microcomposite is intact ($x > u+l_d$)

Stress field in region 2 is derived from the following equations of equilibrium :

$$\frac{d\sigma_F}{dx} = -\frac{2}{r_F} \tau \qquad \frac{d\sigma_M}{dx} = \frac{2}{r_F} \tau \qquad \frac{V_F}{V - V_F} \tag{2}$$

where σ_F and σ_M are the stresses operating on the fiber and the matrix respectively ; r_F is the radius. V_F is the volume fraction of the fiber.

Integrating equations (2) leads to the following relations for σ_F and σ_M along the debond :

$$\sigma_F(x) = \frac{\sigma}{V_F} \left(1 - \frac{a}{1+a} \cdot \frac{x - u - l_0}{l_d - l_0} \right) \qquad x \geq u + l_0 \tag{3}$$

⁽¹⁾ Any functional form for $\alpha(x)$ may be considered

$$\sigma_M(x) = \frac{\sigma}{1 - V_F} \cdot \frac{a}{1 + a} \cdot \frac{x - u - \ell_0}{\ell_d - \ell_0} \quad x \geq u + \ell_0 \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma = \frac{F}{A_\mu}$ (F is the applied force and A_μ is the microcomposite cross sectional area).

$a = \frac{E_M(1 - V_F)}{E_F V_F}$ (E_M and E_F are moduli of the fiber and the matrix respectively). Debond length l_d as a function of applied stress is derived from equation (3) :

$$l_d = \frac{\sigma \cdot a \cdot r_F}{2 \cdot V_F \cdot (1 + a) \cdot (1 - \beta) \cdot (\tau_0 + k\sigma)} \quad \text{where } \beta = \frac{\ell_0}{\ell_d} \quad (5)$$

2.1- Stress-strain relationships

In the presence of n matrix cracks, the microcomposite elongation ($U_T(n, \sigma)$) is the sum of fiber elongations in the debonded regions ($U_F(l_d + u)$) and in the intact regions ($U_{int}(L - 2n(l_d + u))$).

$$U_T(n, \sigma) = U_{int}(L - 2 \cdot n \cdot (l_d + u)) + 2 \cdot n \cdot U_F(l_d + u) \quad (6)$$

where L is microcomposite length

$$\text{where} \quad U_F(\sigma) = \int_0^{u + \ell_d} \frac{\sigma_F}{E_F} \cdot dx \equiv \frac{\sigma \cdot \ell_d}{E_F \cdot V_F} \cdot \left[\frac{u}{\ell_d} + 1 - \frac{a \cdot (1 - \beta)}{2 \cdot (1 + a)} \right] \quad (7)$$

Similarly the following equation is obtained for associated matrix displacements :

$$U_M(\sigma) = \frac{\sigma \cdot \ell_d}{E_M \cdot (1 - V_F)} \cdot \frac{a \cdot (1 - \beta)}{2 \cdot (1 + a)} \quad (8)$$

Difference between fiber elongation (equation (7)) and matrix displacement (equation (8)) provides the matrix crack opening distance :

$$u = (U_F - U_M) = \frac{\sigma \cdot \ell_d}{E_F \cdot V_F - \sigma} \cdot \frac{(1 + \beta)}{2} \quad (9)$$

Inserting expressions for $U_{int}(\dots)$ and U_F into equation (7), microcomposite strains ϵ_T can be expressed in the following simple manner, considering that elongations remain essentially small ($L \approx L_0$, L_0 is the initial length of microcomposite),

$$\epsilon_T = \frac{\sigma}{E_0} \cdot \left[1 + \frac{2 \cdot n \cdot \ell_d \cdot a}{L_0} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma}{E_F V_F - \sigma} + 1 \right) \cdot \frac{(1 + \beta)}{2} \right] \quad (10)$$

where E_0 is the initial Young's modulus of microcomposite.

2.2 Number of matrix cracks and fiber failure :

The number of matrix cracks depends upon the applied stress σ and interfacial characteristics. Probability of failure for the matrix (formation of a single crack) and for the fiber were derived from the following 2-parameter simple Weibull's equation for volume-located fracture origins :

$$P = 1 - \exp \left[- \int \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \cdot dV \right] \quad (11)$$

where m and σ_0 are the statistical parameters.

The probability of formation of a single crack within the i^{th} matrix block delineated by two neighboring matrix cracks, is given by the following equation obtained by inserting description of stress state into equation (11) :

$$P_{M_i} = 1 - \exp \left[- 2S_M \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{0M}} \cdot \frac{a}{V_M \cdot (1+a)} \right)^{m_M} \cdot \left[l_i - \frac{l_{d_i}}{(m+1)} \cdot (m+\beta) \right] \right] \quad (12)$$

where l_{d_i} is the debond length for this i^{th} matrix block and $2l_i$ is block length. A similar approach was applied to determine failure probability of the fiber in the presence of n matrix cracks :

$$P_F^T(n) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{0F}} \cdot \frac{1}{V_F(1+a)} \right)^{m_F} \cdot V_{OF} \left[2n \frac{l_d}{L} A + 1 \right] \right] \quad (13)$$

where

$$A = \left(\left(\frac{u}{l_d} + \beta \right) (1+a)^{m_F} - \frac{1-\beta}{m_F+1} \left(\frac{1-(1+a)^{m_F+1}}{a} \right) - 1 \right)$$

V_{OF} is the volume of the fiber.

3- APPLICATION TO SiC/SiC MICROCOMPOSITES

The stress-strain curves for SiC/SiC microcomposites were computed from equations (10) and (5) as a function of interfacial parameters. The number of cracks was determined as a function of applied stress by means of the probability equation (12). A numerical procedure was employed for generation of random location of matrix cracks [16].

The median matrix block strengths derived from equation (12) were adopted as a criterion for matrix cracking. Median fiber strength was also selected as criterion for fiber failure. The main characteristics for SiC/SiC microcomposites are given in table 1.

Stress-strain curves

Figures 4 and 5 exemplify the influence of fiber/matrix interactions upon the stress-strain curves, which may be summarized as follows : strong fiber/matrix interactions enhance nonlinear deformations, high stresses and a high stress at saturation which tends to coincide with the ultimate strength.

Figure 4 predicts the influence of interfacial shear stress τ_0 . As previously mentioned, the stress-strain curves exhibit a wider nonlinear domain of deformations and a higher stress at saturation with increasing τ_0 . By contrast, the nonlinear domain covers a narrow range of deformations and

the stress at saturation tends to be much lower than ultimate strength when τ_0 decreases. These stress-strain curves thus demonstrate that the stresses are higher in the presence of rather strong fiber/matrix interactions as currently observed on several 2D CVI composites [17].

Furthermore, results are in agreement with data obtained experimentally on 2D SiC/SiC CVI composites. Thus, for those CMCs exhibiting a plateau-like behaviour, τ_0 estimates were smaller than 10 MPa [17]. τ_0 values larger than 100 MPa have been measured on those composites exhibiting high stresses, a wide nonlinear domain of deformations and a stress at saturation close to ultimate strength [17].

Table 1 : Main characteristics of SiC/SiC microcomposites (scatter is indicated in brackets) [4].

V_F	0.26 [0.16 - 0.41]
E_M	300 GPa
E_F	180 GPa
m_M	4.9
m_F	3.9
$\sigma_{OM} (V_0 = 1m^3)$	3
$\sigma_{OF} (V_0 = 1m^3)$	2.5

It can also be seen from figure 4 that propagation of interfacial debond affects significantly the stress-strain curves only in the presence of weak fiber/matrix interactions ($\tau_0 \leq 10$ MPa). This result is in agreement with logical expectation, since it may be foreseen that important propagation of debond is promoted by low interfacial shear stresses.

CONCLUSIONS

Equations relating the interfacial parameters and the stress-strain behaviour were established for microcomposites. Stress-strain relations were derived from fiber elongations in the different regions of the microcomposite delineated by matrix cracking and fiber debonding. Predictions of the stress-strain curves as a function of interfacial parameters evidenced various trends which are readily observed on practical microcomposites and CMCs. Predictions thus showed that strong fiber/matrix interactions (as measured by short interfacial debonds, or significant interfacial shear strength (τ_0)) favour matrix cracking, high stresses and a high stress at saturation which tends to coincide with ultimate strength. In the presence of weaker interfaces, stresses are lower, the nonlinear domain covers a narrow range of deformations, and the stress at saturation is significantly smaller than ultimate strength. Growth of interfacial debond significantly affects the stress-strain curve only in the presence of weak interfaces.

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Figure 1: Typical tensile stress-strain curves obtained on different 2D SiC/SiC composite specimens as a function of interfacial bond.

Figure 2: Typical tensile stress-strain curves obtained on SiC/BN/SiC microcomposites with a range of interfaces. The stress refers to that acting on the fiber at the location of matrix cracks.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram showing the local stress-state in the fiber and in the matrix in the vicinity of a matrix crack. Also shown is the function $\alpha(x)$ used in equation (1).

Figure 4 : Influence of interfacial shear stress upon the stress strain curves of SiC/SiC microcomposites ($\beta = 0$; $k = 0$).

Figure 5 : Prediction of influence of debond length upon the stress-strain curves for SiC/SiC microcomposites ($\beta = 0$; $k = 0$).